

DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING STUDY FOR A SMALL, COMPLEX COMPONENT REQUIRED IN LARGE PRODUCTION VOLUMES

K. D. Potter, A. Towse & M. R. Wisnom

*Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol, Queen's Building,
University Walk, Bristol, BS8 1TR, UK.*

SUMMARY: The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate that it is possible to develop an approach to the design of small, complex, composite components that is driven by the requirements of minimum cost manufacture. The approach depends on identifying those geometrical features that are critical in the required component and allowing the rest of the component geometry to be dictated by the deformation characteristics of the chosen reinforcement. To explore the applicability of this concept a study has been made of one specific component required in large numbers at low cost, to form the node elements in a truss structure for a space-plane application. This application has been studied by both practical manufacture and test of components and by FEA. Both practical test and analysis agree that the design approach gives rise to a structurally acceptable solution of very low manufacturing cost.

KEYWORDS: design for manufacture, reinforcement deformation, finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

Conventional practice in composite component design and manufacture has followed the procedures used with metallic design. That is to say that a design is drawn, analysed and released for manufacture. In view of the constraints that are placed on many designs by the necessity to fit within predetermined geometries this methodology is, in general, the appropriate way to proceed. If rigidly applied this sort of approach can lead to designs that are difficult or costly to manufacture. Additionally, defects can be induced during manufacture if the design does not accurately reflect the capabilities of the reinforcements and processes used and the skill of the labour force used to convert them into components.

Over the years a body of understanding has grown up that defines thicknesses, bend radii, lay-up procedures etc. that serve to minimise the probability of defects in mouldings (ref. 1) and experienced designers will incorporate this understanding into their designs. Utilising these "best practice" approaches to maximise moulding quality does, however, tend to have a negative influence on both the costs of lay-up and the amount of training and support required to be given to shop floor labour. In part offsetting this influence there is increasing stress being laid on design for manufacture and ensuring that the required geometry and properties can be achieved at the minimum costs. One might paraphrase the traditional approach as asking "how can the fibres be persuaded to have the necessary trajectories?". The design for manufacture approach builds on this simply by adding the caveat "at the lowest possible cost" to the above formulation.

This paper describes an alternative approach to the design of composite components and illustrates this by reference to a specific case study. The approach described here is essentially to drive the design process from the manufacturing end, specifically from the geometries that can be formed from the reinforcement with minimal deformation and thus can be manufactured by less skilled labour to high quality standards. Clearly such a methodology cannot be used for the great bulk of components, however where the approach is usable a stable, low cost, high quality result should be obtainable.

Reinforcement Deformability

All reinforcements are capable of some deformation, by a variety of modes and over a wide range of deformations limits (ref. 2). However, when an attempt is made to deform reinforcements it is often found that wrinkling of the reinforcement occurs well before the theoretical deformation limits are reached (ref. 3). The key to successful generation of shapes from hard to form reinforcements lies in minimising the deformation required. Even the limited deformability that is available with unidirectional prepreg can be used to create complex 3D geometries in conjunction with techniques such as curved line folding.

The critical point being made here is not, however, that the complex shapes that we draw on component lay-up diagrams can be made by utilising the deformability of the reinforcements; this is very often simply not the case and substantial tailoring is required with high associated costs. The point is rather that, at least in some cases, an understanding of what the reinforcements would “like” to do can be used to drive the definition of the geometry to be moulded. It should be fairly clear that, if the reinforcement does not have to be extensively tailored, simpler lay-ups should be possible; and that the prospect is held out of lay-up in flat format followed by a simple and rapid forming operation to give the required geometry. The concept of laying up a flat or generically shaped preform followed by a shaping step is not novel (ref. 4), indeed it is central to many applications of RTM processing (ref. 5). However applying the concept of following “natural” deformation paths should greatly reduce the probability of deformation induced defect formation. These deformation induced defects include wrinkles and folds in the preform and are very deleterious to the properties of the cured components. Additionally, if “natural” fibre paths can be generated one would intuitively expect smoother stress distributions, especially in terms of out of plane stresses.

It should be noted that the use of the word “natural” does not imply that no deformations must be imposed, nor that the deformation modes initiated will be those that are required unless some element of control is established. It would be very difficult to determine a rigorous definition of a natural deformation path and for the purposes of this paper we will define it as that deformation path that leads to the minimum deformation to achieve the required geometry. Ideally, one would like to be able to define these “natural” paths analytically so that the application of this concept to part design could form part of the, more or less, normal CAD design approach. Initially, however, it was necessary to test out the concept; to determine whether “natural” paths could be established; to determine the ease of manufacture of components utilising such paths; and to determine the performance of such components.

To meet these aims a demonstrator component was chosen and a mould was manufactured in such a way that the reinforcement could follow a “natural” path. The demonstrator component chosen for this study was a connecting node for a UK based private enterprise one stage to orbit space plane concept, designed by Reaction Engines Limited. The Reaction Engines Skylon vehicle fuselage (refs 6&7) is built up from a trusswork of carbon fibre tubes bonded

together at 10 way nodes. At each node six of the tubes lie essentially in one plane and the other four are out of the plane. In order to ensure that joints can be assembled it is necessary to split the nodes into sections. The main split will be between the six way node element and the four way node element. The six way node element will also have to be split “horizontally” to allow ease of assembly and a relatively simple route to be used for node manufacturing. The necessity for a simple manufacturing route is driven by the fact that around 30,000 nodes are required in one Skylon structure, equating to 60,000 mouldings just for the six way elements. This production volume is far in excess of the volumes normally experienced for high strength composite components. It is generally accepted that no ideal manufacturing routes exist for the mass production of small complex components from high performance composite materials (ref. 8). The work described here was aimed at demonstrating some elements of a suitable manufacturing process. These were; lay-up of a preform in flat format to minimise costs and simplify the development of a suitable automated process, and the conversion of the flat preform into a contoured shape that could function as a node. One critical element in this is that the conversion must not introduce unreliability into the component, the choice of a “natural” fibre path is seen as been critical to this aim of ensuring reliable low cost manufacturing.

DESIGN OF NODE FOR MANUFACTURING STUDY

The basic design chosen is a half shell, split on the mid line of the tubes, with all tubes intersecting on their axis. UD carbon fibre has been chosen as the reinforcement to be used and this is utilised in prepreg form to maximise strength and simplify handling. In keeping with the aim of minimising manufacturing costs through simplicity of design, constant width strips of prepreg are used, the width being set at half the circumference of the relevant tubes. If increased strength is required additional material in the form of woven cloth prepreg could be introduced in the crossover region without disrupting the basic design aim of simplicity. The basic design is as shown in fig 1.

It should be noted that the geometry shown in figure 1 is derived from an attempt to model the geometry produced experimentally using a solid modelling package. The match between experimental and analytical geometry is close but not perfect.

Fig 1. Schematic geometry of the six way node

As can be seen from fig 1, the node may be subject to bending failure when loaded along the arms in tension; due to the out of plane fibre trajectories. To overcome this, several possibilities can be considered. A low density foam can be used to fill the centre part of the node; the two half shells could be held together with a titanium bolt that also serves as the attachment point for the out of plane tube end fittings; a block could be bonded between the two halves during node assembly. This last option was selected for this study.

Definition of Geometry and Mould Tool Manufacture

The basic geometry chosen was 15mm ID for the major tube node connection and 10mm ID for the minor tube node connection. (Dimensions chosen largely for ease of manufacture of a master model) The major and minor tubes intersect on their centre line at an angle of 26.6° ,

see fig 2. A master model to this geometry was acquired and strips of glass fibre/913 epoxy prepreg were then laid up along each arm of the master and taped down to the surface at some distance (~4.5cm) from the intersection point of the node arms. The positions of the tape were adjusted until the fibre trajectories appeared to be smooth without excessive local changes in fibre direction.

Fig 2. Basic dimensions of master model

Fig 3. Approximate dimensions of finished tool

This lay-up was cured at 120⁰C without the application of any pressure. The inside surface of the resulting glass fibre moulding represented the required outside surface of the mould tool. The surface roughness of the GRP was then filled with wax and the GRP shell was used to manufacture a mould tool from Al filled epoxy that could be used at cure temperatures up to 120⁰C, see fig 3.

Lay-up of Reinforcement

The lay-up was selected as 6 plies of reinforcement along each arm of the node, corresponding to 0.75mm cured thickness in the arms.

The reinforcement used for the manufacture of prototypes was XAS/913 prepreg as this had the correct cure temperature. Zero bleed moulding was used in conjunction with vacuum bag moulding to simplify the moulding process as far as possible.

Two approaches were taken to the lay-up of reinforcement on to the mould tool. The first was to lay up directly onto the tool surface forming each ply as it was laid down. This was done primarily to prove out the tool and demonstrate that the geometry of the tool was correct. It proved very easy to lay up the prepreg such that it followed the tool contour. However, there was a tendency for the prepreg to stretch in the 90⁰ direction as it was laid down producing a slightly over width moulding and great care had to be taken to ensure that the edges of subsequent plies of prepreg coincided.

The second approach was to lay up all six plies on a flat surface (without any debulking stage to minimise costs). A 10mm wide strip of prepreg was laid up at the end of each arm at the mid point of the lay-up with the fibre direction across the arm. This strip was intended to counter the tendency of the prepreg to stretch sideways. It proved to be much quicker to lay up the prepreg in flat format and much easier to keep the edges of subsequent plies coincident. Equally, it proved to be very easy to conform the flat prepreg lay-up to the geometry of the tool, although care was needed to ensure that the lay-up stayed central with respect to the

arms of the node. In a production node tool (based on compression rather than vacuum bag moulding) some feature would have to be provided to ensure perfect orientation. A series of mouldings were made using unskilled labour with no previous experience of handling composites. All mouldings appeared to be of high quality with good fibre alignment. The weight of the mouldings was approximately 11 gr. The cost of the manufacturing route cannot currently be quantified as it is intended that a large measure of automation be applied. Even in the absence of this it should be possible to streamline the manufacturing process to give production costs that are acceptable in view of the proposed application.

ASSEMBLY AND TEST OF NODE

The prototype node mouldings were wet assembled into a six way node structure using aluminium rods to simulate the tubes that would be required in the real structure, the adhesive used was 3M9323 a high strength, 120⁰C cure, two part epoxy.

The assembled node was set up in a model 1341 Instron servohydraulic test machine operating under displacement control.

Failure of the bondline in one node arm occurred at 12.56KN. Failure occurred at the CFRP/adhesive interface. The bondline was seen to be partially voided and the rod was offset in the arm as shown in fig 4.

Fig 4. Misalignment of rod with respect to node and position of voidage

Factoring from Reaction Engines data for loads on the Skylon vehicle a load in this arm of 12KN represents the worst case condition. The bond-line failure therefore occurred at 5% above the maximum load. The measured thickness of the node arms was 0.8mm giving a cross sectional area of 27.14mm² at an ID of 10mm. At the failure load of 12.56KN the average stress in the loaded CFRP node arms would be 463MPa and the strain would be 0.35%. The joint strength was 400N/mm of joint width. The test was carried out on one of the pairs of 10mm arms, the deviation of the fibre paths on these arms is greater than for the larger arms so the result for the 10mm arms should also be indicative for the 15mm arms. From previous work on bonded joints (ref. 9) the mode of failure exhibited in this joint is unexpected. The most likely modes of failure are adhesive cracking for joints with large fillets and adhesive cracking/delamination in the CFRP for joints with small or no fillets. The release agent used on the node tool was mould wax, because of the tendency for cast moulds to have slightly rough and porous surfaces. It is possible that a transfer of this release agent occurred and that insufficient material was removed from the CFRP to guarantee a good bonding surface. It should be possible to greatly improve on the bond strength exhibited in this test by improvements in surface preparation and better geometry at the end of the joint.

Visual and microscopic examination (up to x 100) of the tested node showed no damage as a result of the test on the outside surface of the node. It would not be possible to disassemble the bonded node without damage, so the condition of the inside of the node is unknown. The out of plane misalignment of the prepreg in the node in the cross-over regions at the centre of the node will increase from the inside to the outside of the node. As the most likely form of damage would be cracking and delamination at these cross-over regions the absence of damage on the outside is strongly indicative that no damage will be seen on the inside of the

node. The indication is therefore that the node has some strength in reserve in the mode tested. It is not possible to determine what level of strength reserve is available at this time.

Despite the great simplicity of the design from the manufacturing viewpoint it has proven to be much more difficult to model the geometry analytically to permit FEA. The procedure that was arrived at to model the geometry on I-Deas is outlined below.

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

The geometry is as depicted in Fig 5. Only one dimension was taken from the final moulding, and this was the dimensions of the (assumed) arc ADB of Fig 5. This arc was used to locate point B in space, the only other line which was known was the straight line AE which extends out along the top of the Dia 15 arm of the node. The surface was built in sections, with the lines BC and EC related to the circumference of the semicircle on the Dia 10 arm and the quarter circle on the Dia 15 arm respectively. Hence, BC was constrained to be $(\pi \cdot 10/2)$, or 15.71mm and EC to be $(\pi \cdot 15/4)/(\cos(26.6^\circ))$ or 13.17mm in length. In this way, the surface has not stretched in the transverse fibre direction and therefore the fibre trajectories as modelled by the software will bear close relation to the practical moulding. The length of the arms was 45mm from the centre to the end of the flared section, as indicated previously.

A quarter model was used, which was meshed using eight-noded quadratic quadrilateral shells wherever possible, and quadratic triangle shell elements where necessary. The fibre trajectories were based on the underlying CAD part, and were seen to bear close resemblance to what would be expected in the actual moulding, although no data is available to support this.

Fig 5. FE quarter model schematic

Element Formulation

As would be expected from the previous discussion on the lay-up, the moulding is neither balanced nor symmetric. Furthermore, although the tooled surface is smooth, the outside surface alters between 6, 12 and 18 ply thickness. Consequently, four lay-ups were used in the model, as depicted in Fig 6. The main arms (light grey) were $[0^\circ]_6$, area CEF was $[0,-63]_6$, area BDF was $[0,+53]_6$ and ADFE was $[0,+53,-63]_6$. All these lay-ups are relative to the local directions which were defined in I-Deas, as shown in Fig 7, and are referred to as lay-ups A,B,C and D respectively.

It can be seen from Fig 6 that between 6 and 12 'null' plies have been included to ensure the correct offset between areas of differing lay-up in the model.

The lay-up for each area was input into the I-Deas FE program, which calculated the A,B and D matrices from Classical Laminate Theory. The properties of each individual lamina in the lay-up were based on unidirectional T800-924 from Hexcel, as this material would be used in production. The null material was taken to be 1% of the elastic moduli of the T800.

Fig 6. Model lay-ups

Fig 7. Local element 'x' direction

Analysis and Results

A linear elastic analysis was carried out with mechanical loadcases of 8kN on the dia 15 arm, and 4kN on the dia 10 arm (equivalent to 32kN and 8kN tension/tension for the full node). Symmetric boundary conditions were applied along the cut edges, and a rigid tube was modelled at the centre of the node as shown in Fig 5 as mentioned earlier.

The greatest cause for concern in terms of the stresses in the node was seen to be the transverse tensile stresses on ply 1, the inside surface of the main diameter 15 arm. As the tensile load is applied, the node will attempt to straighten out, resulting in a bending moment on the main arm.

This will place ply 1 into transverse tension, and ply 6 into transverse compression. It was seen from the results that the loading in the transverse direction on the dia 15 arm was not pure bending, but approximately 59MPa of transverse tensile membrane stress was also present. The stresses from the mechanical load on the main arm are shown in Fig 8.

Fig 8. Transverse tensile and intralaminar shear for main arm under tensile loading (MPa)

It can be seen from Fig 8 that a peak transverse tensile stress of 205MPa acts on the unidirectional main arm. This stress is driven directly from the geometry of the flare of the node. It is highly likely that a transverse crack would appear in the arm at relatively low loads, which, as the lay-up is UD, would rapidly crack the remaining plies until the main arm would split into two pieces. The consequences of such a crack on the structural integrity of the node (especially under compressive loading) would be severe.

It can also be seen that a high in-plane (intralaminar) shear stress is present at the end of the node, due to the differing axial stiffness of the main arm centreline and edge. This results in a

non-uniform stress distribution, with the top (initially straight) edge carrying most of the load, with the free (curved) edge carrying essentially no load. A large deflection, non-linear analysis would be needed to see this curved edge begin to pick up load. This has not been carried out to date.

It was also seen that the 'B' lay-up $[0,-63]_6$ also suffered from high transverse tensile stresses on ply 1, due to bending of the section caused by the offset in neutral axes between lay-ups A and B.

Suggested Modified Lay-Up

In light of the high transverse tensile stresses seen in the model, the logical solution was to stiffen the unidirectional arms to both membrane stresses and against bending. The easiest way to achieve this would be by placing a single 90° ply as far away from the neutral axis as possible.

To minimise deformation of this extra ply between areas of differing lay-up, it was decided to place the 90° material on the tool edge side of the neutral axis. Ideally (from a bending stiffness viewpoint) this would mean ply 1, although that would mean bonding directly to a 90° ply, which was believed to be disadvantageous. The compromise was to include an extra 90° layer to the lay-up at ply 3, meaning the lay-ups were now (from the tooled surface):

$$\begin{array}{ll} A': [0]_2[90][0]_4[\text{null}]_{14} & B': [0,-63]_2[90,+26.6][0,-63]_4[\text{null}]_7 \\ C': [0,53]_2[90,-37][0,53]_4[\text{null}]_7 & D': [0,53,-63]_2[90,-37,+26.6][0,53,-63]_4 \end{array}$$

The analysis was repeated with these new lay-ups, and it was seen that the peak transverse tension in the main arm was reduced from 205MPa to 131MPa (a reduction of 36%). The stress distribution was now almost pure bending, with ply 3 (the 90° layer) picking up the membrane stresses. The level of the transverse tension is, therefore, reduced, but is still at a level at which ply cracking can be expected from the tooled surface under tensile loading. However, the consequences of this First Ply Failure (FPF) would now not be as severe as the 90° ply is likely to arrest transverse cracks from jumping from ply 2 to ply 4. The B' lay-up peak transverse tension was also reduced, from 169MPa to 120MPa (a reduction of 29%), although it is still well above that required to crack the ply. Again, the lay-up here is sufficiently multidirectional to ensure that this FPF would probably not lead to global failure.

The main thrust of this paper has been the fact that the geometry has been driven by what is practically quick and easy to achieve, and by what the fibres 'naturally' wish to deform into. To demonstrate the difference compared with a node designed without considering the manufacture of the node, a second FE model was built based simply on interconnecting tubes filleted together, as shown in Fig 10. A diam 15 tube was intersected by two diameter 10 tubes, which were then filleted with 8mm and 6mm fillet radii. It was assumed that a similar method to that used before would be used to manufacture the node, i.e. laying down strips of material for each arm, and to that end the surfaces were trimmed to ensure the reinforcement widths did not alter. This resulted in the same lay-ups A,B,C and D as before, but with different shapes as shown in Fig 10 (e.g. EFC is again the $[0,-63]_6$ lay-up).

Fig 10. Conventional CAD geometry

The results from the stress analysis showed generally higher transverse tensile and intralaminar shear stresses, especially in the highly deformed B lay-up. At this point the peak transverse tension increased from 169MPa (for the standard lay-up manufacture-led node) to 213MPa (for this filleted tube version), an increase of 26%. The stresses in other parts of the model showed slight worsening of performance over the manufacture-led node, with the exception of the main arm. As noted previously, high transverse tensile stresses were encountered in the inside surface of the main arm under tensile load due to the flare out of the node arm. This transverse tension is purely geometry driven, and as the filleted tube version has no long sweep, the transverse tension is lower (at 157MPa cf. 205MPa for the 'good' design). It must be noted, however, that this value of 157MPa is still too high and a 90° ply would still be required. It must be emphasised that there would be considerable difficulties involved in the manufacture of defect free nodes to this design.

GENERAL DISCUSSION

The prototyping exercise reported here has been entirely driven by low cost manufacturing considerations based around the concept of designing the component and mould tool around the geometries easily available from the reinforcement. Initial test results indicate that the design can carry the required load in tension straight across the node in one pair of arms. No effort has currently been made to establish the adequacy of the design in compression across the node. Even if the design requires modification the basic concepts of laying up a prepreg preform in the flat state and deforming this onto a tool whose dimensions have been chosen for ease of forming should be retained as it is these features that lead to controllable costs and quality.

It has been assumed above that a measure of automation of the lay-up process will be required in a production environment. The symmetry of the node preform would allow several nodes to be laid up at once, either manually or by tape-layer. Simple changes to lay-up practices such as this should have major impacts on overall economics.

CONCLUSIONS

For at least some components the concept of designing the geometry to follow the characteristics of the reinforcement has been demonstrated.

1. This has been demonstrated via the manufacture of a complex composite node.
2. In this case the geometry was only fixed at the load introduction points and allowed to follow “natural” paths elsewhere.
3. The design is quick to produce and good results can be obtained with unskilled labour.
4. Testing has shown that the design is capable of carrying the required tensile end load in arms that are directly opposite across the node.
5. The performance of the node has yet to be established in terms of compressive loads or loads applied between adjacent arms.
6. The theoretical performance of the node has been seen to be lacking in strength when subjected to large tensile loads due to the flare of the main arm. It has further been demonstrated that the inclusion of a 90° ply is beneficial to the overall stress state in the node, to a point where it is capable of carrying the loads required of it.
7. The standard CAD geometry based node is seen to be inferior in stress state to the manufacture-led node, but only marginally so. The important point to remember is that the CAD part contains large deformations, and it is almost inevitable that the moulded node to this shape would contain splits and wrinkles. The manufacture led node is, by definition, extremely quick and easy to prepare as well as being superior in performance to what would have been designed without paying attention to design for manufacture.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to acknowledge the support of the UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council, via contract number GRK66833

REFERENCES

1. Hart-Smith. L. (1988) *Designing with advanced fibrous composites*. Proc Australian Bicentennial International Congress in Mechanical Engineering.
2. Potter. K.D., (1979) *The influence of accurate stretch data for reinforcements on the production of complex structural mouldings. Part 1. Deformation of aligned sheets and fabrics*. Composites. July 1979. pp 161-7
3. Potter, K.D. (1980) *Deformation mechanisms of fibre reinforcements and their influence on the fabrication of structural parts*. Advances in composite materials. (eds A.R. Bunsell, C. Bathias. A. Martrenchar, D. Menkes, G.Verchery) Pergamon Press. pp 1564-79
4. Potter. K. D., & Robertson. F. C. (1987) *Bismaleimide formulations for resin transfer moulding*. 32nd International SAMPE Symposium. April.
5. Morgan. D. (1989) *Design of an aero-engine thrust reverser blocker door*. Proc 34th International SAMPE Symposium. 2358-64.
6. Varvill. R. (1995) *The Skylon spaceplane*. Proc 46th International Astronautical Congress. Oslo. Paper IAA 95-V3.07 International Astronautical Federation.
7. Bond. A & Varvill R (1995) *Skylon operations and economics*. Proc 46th International Astronautical Congress. Oslo. Paper IAA 95-IAA.1.1.07 International Astronautical Federation.
8. Potter. K.D. (1983) *High rate reforming of thermoplastic laminate into small, complex components; a process study*. Proc 4th International Conference, SAMPE European Chapter. SAMPE. pp 103-12.
9. Adams R.D., Atkins R.W., Harris J.A. & Kinloch A.J. Stress analysis and failure properties of carbon-fibre reinforced plastic/steel double lap joints, J. Adhesion (1986) 20 p.29-53